

Physical Education Teachers' Learned Helplessness, Job and Life Satisfaction Levels During the Covid-19 Pandemic

Seymanur BAGKESEN¹

¹Mersin University, Faculty of Sports Sciences, Mersin, TÜRKİYE

Orcid: 0000-0002-0072-1313

e-mail: seymanurbircan@gmail.com

Assoc. Prof. Fatma CEPIKKURT²

²Mersin University, Faculty of Sports Sciences, Mersin, TÜRKİYE

Orcid: 0000-0002-9096-2873

e-mail: fcepikkurt@mersin.edu.tr

<i>Submission received</i>	<i>Revised</i>	<i>Accepted</i>	<i>Published</i>
14.04.2025	20.05.2025	06.06.2025	30.06.2025

Abstract

This study was conducted to measure physical education teachers' learned helplessness, job satisfaction, and life satisfaction, as well as to determine the relationship between these factors, during the Covid-19 pandemic. The sample consisted of 333 physical education teachers (234 males and 99 females) working in public and private institutions in the city of Mersin, Turkey during the spring term of the 2020-2021 academic year. The "Learned Helplessness Scale", "Minnesota Job Satisfaction Scale", and "Life Satisfaction Scale" were used to collect the data. Descriptive statistics, independent samples t-test, one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA), Pearson Correlation, and regression analysis were employed for statistical analysis, with 0.05 considered the margin of error. The results of the descriptive analysis indicated that the learned helplessness levels of the participants were moderate, their intrinsic job satisfaction levels were high, and their extrinsic job satisfaction and life satisfaction levels were moderate. With respect to gender, men's learned helplessness levels were higher than those of the female participants. The learned helplessness scores of teachers over 45 years old were higher than those of the under 35 and 35-44-year-old age groups. Concerning intrinsic job satisfaction and life satisfaction, participants over the age of 45 scored significantly higher than those under 35. According to the results of the correlation analysis, learned helplessness scores were correlated in the same direction with all variables except intrinsic job satisfaction; the latter was correlated in the same direction with the other variables. As the levels of extrinsic job satisfaction increased, an increase in life satisfaction and intrinsic helplessness levels was also observed. Finally, according to the regression analysis, learned helplessness and job satisfaction were found to predict life satisfaction by 24.8%. Our analyses determined that as the intrinsic helplessness levels of the participants decreased, their extrinsic helplessness levels increased, while intrinsic job satisfaction was found to be the most important predictor of life satisfaction. Compared with the results of previous studies, the participating teachers' learned helplessness and job satisfaction levels during the pandemic were elevated, while no significant change was observed in their life satisfaction levels. Gender was determined not to affect job satisfaction or life satisfaction, age was shown to be a significant variable, and learned helplessness, job satisfaction, and life satisfaction were revealed to be interrelated psychological variables.

Keywords: Physical education teacher, Pandemic, learned helplessness, Job satisfaction, Life satisfaction.

Corresponding author: Seymanur BAGKESEN, **E-mail:** seymanurbircan@gmail.com

*This study was produced from a master's thesis published in 2021 with thesis number 691886.

INTRODUCTION

Epidemics have threatened and continue to threaten human and animal life throughout history. The first known epidemics date back to Before Common Era (BCE). Epidemics such as the plague, smallpox, malaria, flu, cholera, typhoid, AIDS, etc., have affected public health in the realms of sociology, psychology, the economy, religion, education, and politics as well as physiologically. They have led to the collapse of states and upheavals in leadership and triggered mass migrations and famine (Arslan, 2020; Parıldar, 2020). A pandemic is defined as the global spread of an infectious disease. The term is derived from the ancient Greek word *pandemos*, comprised of the roots *pan*, meaning “all”, and *demos*, “people”. Since microorganisms that cause a pandemic may be transmitted from one species to another, from animals to humans, or originate in the soil, air, or water, it is contagious (Arslan, 2020). The current Coronavirus (Covid-19) pandemic has adversely affected virtually every aspect of human existence in its rapid spread across the globe, much as science, information, technology, transportation, and communication have progressed in this century at an ever-accelerating pace. One of the critical sectors affected by the pandemic has been education. In Turkey (and elsewhere), education and training have come to somewhat of an impasse, as responses to the pandemic have resulted in numerous problems, such as the loss of sustainability of in-person education, the transition to online (computer-assisted) education, the inability of some students to access the necessary infrastructure, and the inability to adapt to online instruction. Education/teaching activities consist of three main elements: the student, the teacher, and the program itself, the former two being the most affected by the educational process. The teacher undertakes important duties such as arranging educational environments, coordinating other elements pertaining to their teaching, choosing appropriate teaching methods and strategies, establishing successful human relations with the educational context, and motivating students. Because of the centrality of these duties to the instructional process, the teacher is considered the most strategic element in realizing the aims of education (Alıç, 1995). As a critical element in the educational process, the teacher interacts with both the system itself and the students. This interaction affects the teacher's own characteristics, psychological state, successes or failures, and job and life satisfaction. Teachers' dissatisfaction with their working conditions may push them towards passive behaviors and despair. Many sociologists, especially Karl Marx, have criticized the management class, claiming that “working conditions alienate people from their work and cause passive behavior”. Proponents of the neo-classical management approach argued that working conditions in the 1930s turned employees into passive, helpless people who did their jobs without questioning (Tayfur, 2011). These negative qualities may develop into passive

behaviors, which then in turn passive behaviors may become learned helplessness, a concept experienced by many people or institutions although not widely known in daily life. Learned helplessness results when an individual comes to understand that there is no connection between a behavior and the result of this behavior and hence does not do what is necessary when similar situations arise; this psychological state affects the professional and private lives of teachers (Aydın, 1985). In schools, productivity is not measured using any kind of physical tools, equipment, or other tangible items; rather, it is measured by the affective, conceptual, perceptual, and behavioral changes that occur in the student during the educational process. Productivity in educational institutions is only possible if teachers are satisfied with their work and as a result are motivated to achieve organizational goals (Tura, 2012). Numerous studies have shown that employees with high job and life satisfaction scores are more productive, have more regular social interactions, are more enthusiastic towards their jobs, and more satisfied and engaged with their work with feelings of success and pride (Arasan, 2010; Deveci, 2014; Karababa, 2012; Ozguven, 2003). Job satisfaction and life satisfaction are interrelated, affecting each other, since life satisfaction as a general concept covers the entire life of the individual, including time spent at work, which represents a large part of life. Moreover, for many people, work has become the center of their existence. Satisfaction/dissatisfaction, happiness/unhappiness, willingness (or not) to act, the realization of one's dreams or disappointment concerning work may all affect an individual's relationships with their environment, family, friends, and social life, and in adverse circumstances may impair their mental and physical health (Çetinkanat, 2000). A subject of curiosity has been the effect of home confinement during the pandemic on teachers, who ordinarily would leave their homes every day for school, but instead have remained at home, not teaching physical education classes, which require physical activity and are normally conducted in person. How do the teachers feel, do they find physical education and sports lessons productive in such circumstances? Will levels of learned helplessness increase as teachers internalize negative situations? Will all these negativities affect their job and life satisfaction? Previous studies have shown that teachers' interests, desires, attitudes, and needs in working life have affected their psychological state and changed their job satisfaction and life satisfaction. Taking into account the findings of these studies, teachers' learned helplessness levels and job and life satisfaction are understood to be affected by each other. Proceeding from these explanations, the primary aim of this study was to determine the learned helplessness, job satisfaction, and life satisfaction levels of physical education teachers as well as to discover the relationship between these variables. A further objective was to test whether physical education teachers' levels of learned helplessness, job

satisfaction, and life satisfaction levels differ according to gender, age, whether or not they chose their profession of their own volition, and whether they are hopeful that the pandemic will come to an end.

METHODS

Research Model

This was a cross-sectional study employing the correlational screening method, a quantitative method. Research conducted to measure the correlation between two or more variables is termed correlational research. Studies using the screening method involve comparatively larger sample groups to determine participants' opinions regarding existing, ongoing phenomena or events or identify characteristics of the participants, such as their interests, abilities, skills, and/or attitudes. (Büyüköztürk, Kılıç-Çakmak, Akgün, Karadeniz and Demirel, 2017).

Population-Sample

The study population consisted of 1,020 physical education teachers working in the province of Mersin, Turkey, while the subpopulation was comprised of 546 physical education teachers employed in the central districts of Yenişehir, Mezitli, Toroslar, and Akdeniz. A total of 334 physical education teachers working in the central districts, who were reached using the appropriate sampling method, constituted the study sample. Following the removal of data that distorted a normal distribution, the analysis proceeded based on the data of 333 participants.

As can be seen in Table 1, 29.7% (n = 99) of the participants were female and 70.3% (n = 234) were male. Those under the age of 35 comprised 37.8% (n = 126) of the total number of participants, 37.5% (n = 125) were aged 35-44, and 24.7% (n = 82) were over 45 years old.

Data Collection Tools

A personal information form was created by the researcher especially for the present study. In addition, the "Learned Helplessness Scale" and "Minnesota Job Satisfaction Scale and Life Satisfaction Scale" were also utilized. Detailed information regarding these measurement tools used is presented below.

The personal information form was used to gather data on the independent variables examined in this study, those being gender, age, whether or not the profession was chosen willingly, and whether or not the participant was hopeful that the pandemic will come to an end.

The "Learned Helplessness Scale" (LHS) is a 20-item questionnaire originally developed by Quinless and Nelson (1988) and adapted for Turkish by Yavaş (2012). The Turkish version, for which exploratory and confirmatory factor analyses were also conducted by Yavaş, incorporates a 5-point Likert-type scale to score 15 items. The highest score that can be obtained from this 15-item scale is 75, while the lowest is 15. High total scores indicate elevated levels of learned helplessness. The results of the reliability analysis (Cronbach's alpha coefficients) were as follows: overall score = 0.80, intrinsic helplessness subscale = 0.76, and extrinsic helplessness subscale = 0.75. For the present study, Cronbach's alpha

coefficients for the overall score and intrinsic and extrinsic helplessness subscales were 0.57, 0.78, and 0.74, respectively.

An abbreviated version of the “Minnesota Job Satisfaction Scale” was developed by Davis et al. (1967) (as cited in Baycan, 1985). The reliability and validity study for the Turkish version was performed by Baycan (1985); the Cronbach’s alpha value was 0.77. In the present study, a Cronbach’s alpha value of 0.88 was calculated for intrinsic job satisfaction, while that of extrinsic job satisfaction was 0.83. The Minnesota Job Satisfaction Scale consists of 20 items and two subscales (intrinsic, based on personal factors, and extrinsic, related to environmental factors) that determine the overall level of job satisfaction. The scale is scored using a five-point Likert-type system with values ranging from 1 to 5 points, such that 3 represents a neutral satisfaction score. If the score obtained from the scale is less than 3, job satisfaction is considered low, whereas a value of 4 or greater indicates a high level of satisfaction. There are no reverse questions on the scale.

The validity and reliability study of the Turkish version of the “Satisfaction with Life Scale” (SWLS), developed by Diener, Emmons, Larsen, and Griffin (1985), was conducted by Dağlı and Baysal (2016). The original scale is in English and involves a single factor structure consisting of five items. For the Turkish translation of the scale, the language, measurement and evaluation, and content evaluation were all reviewed by experts. The Cronbach’s alpha intrinsic consistency coefficient of the scale was 0.88 and the test-retest reliability was 0.97 (Baysal & Dağlı, 2016). For the current study, a value of 0.89 was calculated for Cronbach’s alpha coefficient. The lowest score that can be obtained from this scale is 5 and the maximum is 35. Low scores indicate low levels of life satisfaction while high scores denote the opposite.

Data Collection

Prior to the start of the study, approval was obtained from Mersin University Humanities Ethics Committee. Permission to proceed was then granted by the Mersin Governor's Office through Mersin University Rectorate, after which data were collected on a voluntary basis from 334 teachers working in the central Mersin districts of Yenişehir, Toroslar, Mezitli, and Akdeniz during the 2020-2021 academic year, employing electronic scales, and with the help of social media groups. Thanks to the use of the electronic scales, the participating teachers were able to complete the questionnaires at their convenience. The response time for the scales averaged approximately 15 minutes.

Data Analysis

In order to analyze the data, a normality test was first performed. After determining that the data exhibited normal distribution, descriptive statistics were employed and Pearson Product-Moment and regression analyses were conducted to determine the relationships between the scales. For pairwise comparisons, the independent samples t-test was used, while analysis of variance (ANOVA) tests were performed for multiple (three or more) comparisons. A value of $p < .05$ was considered statistically significant.

FINDINGS

Table 1. Demographic information of teachers participating in the study

Variables	n	%
Gender	Female	29.7
	Male	70.3
Age	Under 35	37.8
	35 – 44 years	37.5
	45 and over	24.7
Total	333	100

The study population consisted of 1,020 physical education teachers working in the province of Mersin, Turkey, while the subpopulation was comprised of 546 physical education teachers employed in the central districts of Yenişehir, Mezitli, Toroslar, and Akdeniz. A total of 334 physical education teachers working in the central districts, who were reached using the appropriate sampling method, constituted the study sample. Following the removal of data that distorted a normal distribution, the analysis proceeded based on the data of 333 participants.

As can be seen in Table 1, 29.7% (n = 99) of the participants were female and 70.3% (n = 234) were male. Those under the age of 35 comprised 37.8% (n = 126) of the total number of participants, 37.5% (n = 125) were aged 35-44, and 24.7% (n = 82) were over 45 years old.

Table 2. Descriptive Statistics And Normality Test Results Of Teachers' Scores From Scales And Subscales

Scale	n	Min	Max	\bar{x}	Std. Dev.	Skewness	Kurtosis
Learned helplessness	333	31.00	63.00	45.76	5.21	.657	.717
Intrinsic job satisfaction	333	1.67	5.00	4.19	.61	-.831	.523
Extrinsic job satisfaction	333	1.50	5.00	3.58	.78	-.341	-.350
Life satisfaction	333	1.00	7.00	4.67	1.36	-.351	-.218
Intrinsic helplessness	333	2.43	5.00	4.17	.51	-.345	-.247
Extrinsic helplessness	333	1.00	4.13	2.06	.62	.664	.184

As shown in Table 2, the participating teachers' learned helplessness levels were moderate, intrinsic job satisfaction was high, and extrinsic job satisfaction and life satisfaction were moderate. Since the results of the normality test generated skewness and kurtosis values ranging between +1.50 and -1.50, the distribution of the scales was accepted as normal.

Table 3. T-Test Results Of The Comparison of Teachers' Scale Scores By Gender

Variables	Gender	N	\bar{x}	Std. Dev.	t	SD	p
Learned helplessness	Female	99	44.87	4.56	-2,036	331	.043*
	Male	234	46.14	5.43			
Intrinsic job satisfaction	Female	99	4.20	.66	.339	331	.735
	Male	234	4.18	.59			
Extrinsic job satisfaction	Female	99	3.52	.82	-.908	331	.365
	Male	234	3.60	.76			
Life satisfaction	Female	99	4.43	1.54	-1.956	331	.052
	Male	234	4.77	1.26			
Intrinsic helplessness	Female	99	4.11	.53	-1.482	331	.139
	Male	234	4.20	.50			
Extrinsic helplessness	Female	99	2.01	.54	-1.042	331	.298
	Male	234	2.08	.65			

* $P < 0,05$

According to the independent sample t-test results presented in Table 3, the learned helplessness levels of the teachers differed significantly in terms of gender, with those of the male teachers being higher than those of the female teachers ($t = -2.036$, $p = .43$). Consequently, the male teachers may be assumed to experience learned helplessness more intensely. As regards the other variables examined in this study, the mean scores for intrinsic job satisfaction ($t = .339$, $p = .735$), extrinsic job satisfaction ($t = -.908$, $p = .365$), life satisfaction ($t = -1.956$, $p = .52$), intrinsic helplessness ($t = -1.482$), $p = .139$), and extrinsic helplessness ($t = 1.42$, $p = .298$) did not differ significantly with respect to gender.

Table 4. ANOVA Results Of The Comparison Of Teachers' Scale Scores By Age

Variable	Age Group	N	\bar{x}	Std. Dev.	Sum of Squares	SD	Mean of the Squares	f	P	Source of the Difference	
Learned helplessness	1) Under 35	126	3.00	.32	Between groups	1.297	2	.649			
	2) 35-44 years	125	3.02	.33	Within groups	38.80	330	.118	5.515	.004*	1-3 2-3
	3) 45 and over	82	3.15	.38	Total	40.10	332				
Intrinsic job satisfaction	1) Under 35	126	4.11	.59	Between groups	2.513	2	1.256			
	2) 35-44 years	125	4.16	.68	Within groups	123.740	330	.375	3.351	.036*	1-3
	3) 45 and over	82	4.33	.51	Total	126.253	332				
Extrinsic job satisfaction	1) Under 35	126	3.56	.73	Between groups	.734	2	.367			
	2) 35-44 years	125	3.54	.85	Within groups	201.573	330	.611	.601	.549	-
	3) 45 and over	82	3.66	.73	Total	202.307	332				

Bagkesen, S., and Cepikkurt, F.. (2025). Physical Education Teachers' Learned Helplessness, Job and Life Satisfaction Levels During the Covid-19 Pandemic. *International Journal of Holistic Health, Sports and Recreation*, 4(1), 37-56.

Life satisfaction	1) Under 35	126	4.43	1.33	Between groups	14.622	2	7.311			
	2) 35-44 years	125	4.71	1.34	Within groups	600.520	330	1.820	4.018	.019*	1-3
	3) 45 and over	82	4.97	1.36	Total	615.143	332				
Intrinsic helplessness	1) Under 35	126	4.12	.48	Between groups	1.187	2	.593			
	2) 35-44 years	125	4.16	.55	Within groups	87.677	330	.266	2.233	.109	-
	3) 45 and over	82	4.27	.49	Total	88.864	332				
Extrinsic helplessness	1) Under 35	126	2.02	.55	Between groups	1.476	2	.736			
	2) 35-44 years	125	2.02	.55	Within groups	128.136	330	.388	1.900	.151	-
	3) 45 and over	82	2.18	.78	Total	129.611	332				

* $P < 0,05$

Based on the one-way ANOVA results given in Table 4, teachers' learned helplessness ($F = 5.15, p = .004$), intrinsic job satisfaction ($F = 3.351, p = 0.036$) and life satisfaction ($F = 4.018, p = .019$) levels all differed with respect to age. As a result of the Post-Hoc Tukey HSD (honestly significant difference) analysis carried out to determine between which categories the difference was observed, teachers over the age of 45 had higher levels of learned helplessness than teachers under the age of 35 and between the ages of 35-44. Teachers over the age of 45 were also found to exhibit higher levels of intrinsic job satisfaction and life satisfaction than teachers under the age of 35.

Table 5. T-Test Results Of The Comparison Of Teachers' Scale And Subscale Scores By Whether They Chose Their Profession Of Their Own Volition Or Not

Variable	Group	n	\bar{x}	Std. Dev.	t	SD	P																																																								
Learned helplessness	Positive	275	45.76	5.18	-.011	331	.991																																																								
	Negative	58	45.77	5.39				Intrinsic job satisfaction	Positive	275	4.25	.58	4.025	331	.000**	Negative	58	3.90	.68	Extrinsic job satisfaction	Positive	275	3.64	.73	2.685	331	.009*	Negative	58	3.29	.91	Life satisfaction	Positive	275	4.88	1.27	6.408	331	.000**	Negative	58	3.69	1.34	Intrinsic helplessness	Positive	275	4.20	.51	1.739	331	.083	Negative	58	4.07	.52	Extrinsic helplessness	Positive	275	2.04	.62	-1.269	331	.205
Intrinsic job satisfaction	Positive	275	4.25	.58	4.025	331	.000**																																																								
	Negative	58	3.90	.68				Extrinsic job satisfaction	Positive	275	3.64	.73	2.685	331	.009*	Negative	58	3.29	.91	Life satisfaction	Positive	275	4.88	1.27	6.408	331	.000**	Negative	58	3.69	1.34	Intrinsic helplessness	Positive	275	4.20	.51	1.739	331	.083	Negative	58	4.07	.52	Extrinsic helplessness	Positive	275	2.04	.62	-1.269	331	.205	Negative	58	2.15	.59								
Extrinsic job satisfaction	Positive	275	3.64	.73	2.685	331	.009*																																																								
	Negative	58	3.29	.91				Life satisfaction	Positive	275	4.88	1.27	6.408	331	.000**	Negative	58	3.69	1.34	Intrinsic helplessness	Positive	275	4.20	.51	1.739	331	.083	Negative	58	4.07	.52	Extrinsic helplessness	Positive	275	2.04	.62	-1.269	331	.205	Negative	58	2.15	.59																				
Life satisfaction	Positive	275	4.88	1.27	6.408	331	.000**																																																								
	Negative	58	3.69	1.34				Intrinsic helplessness	Positive	275	4.20	.51	1.739	331	.083	Negative	58	4.07	.52	Extrinsic helplessness	Positive	275	2.04	.62	-1.269	331	.205	Negative	58	2.15	.59																																
Intrinsic helplessness	Positive	275	4.20	.51	1.739	331	.083																																																								
	Negative	58	4.07	.52				Extrinsic helplessness	Positive	275	2.04	.62	-1.269	331	.205	Negative	58	2.15	.59																																												
Extrinsic helplessness	Positive	275	2.04	.62	-1.269	331	.205																																																								
	Negative	58	2.15	.59																																																											

* $P < 0,05$; ** $P < 0,01$

As shown in Table 5, for the teachers who chose their profession of their own volition, intrinsic job satisfaction ($t = 4.025, p = .000$), extrinsic job satisfaction ($t = 2.685, p = .009$) and life satisfaction ($t = 6.408, p = .000$) scores were found to be significantly higher. However, no significant differences were observed in the learned helplessness or subscale scores, which represent the other variables of the study, with respect to whether the teachers willingly chose their profession.

Table 6. T-Test Results Of The Comparison Of Teachers' Scale And Subscale Scores Based On Whether The Teachers Were Hopeful That The Pandemic Will End

Variable	Group	N	\bar{x}	Std. Dev.	t	SD	p
Learned helplessness	Positive	233	45.84	5.15	.387	331	.699
	Negative	100	45.60	5.37			
Intrinsic job satisfaction	Positive	233	4.25	.60	2.646	331	.009*
	Negative	100	4.05	.62			
Extrinsic job satisfaction	Positive	233	3.65	.75	2.488	331	.013*
	Negative	100	3.42	.82			
Life satisfaction	Positive	233	4.77	1.38	1.925	331	.055
	Negative	100	4.45	1.29			
Intrinsic helplessness	Positive	233	4.23	.53	3.195	331	.002*
	Negative	100	4.05	.45			
Extrinsic helplessness	Positive	233	2.02	.63	-1.753	331	.081
	Negative	100	2.15	.60			

* $P < 0,05$

According to Table 6, the teachers who expressed hope that the pandemic will come to an end scored higher on intrinsic job satisfaction ($t = 2.646, p < .05$) and extrinsic job satisfaction ($t = 2.488, p < .05$) than those who felt hopeless. With regard to intrinsic helplessness, the hopeful teachers were found to have significantly higher levels than the hopeless teachers ($t = 3.195, p < .05$).

Table 7. Pearson Correlation Analysis Results Concerning The Relationship Between Teachers' Learned Helplessness, Job Satisfaction, And Life Satisfaction

	1.	2.	3.	4.	5.	6.
1. Learned helplessness						
2. Intrinsic job satisfaction	.062					
	.258					
3. Extrinsic job satisfaction	.253**	.696**				
	.000	.000				
4. Life satisfaction	.199**	.461**	.428**			
	.000	.000	.000			
5. Intrinsic helplessness	.405**	.438**	.307**	.311**		
	.000	.000	.000	.000		
6. Extrinsic helplessness	.749**	-.253**	.042	-.018	-.302**	
	.000	.000	.450	.745	.000	
Mean	3.05	4.19	3.58	4.67	4.17	2.06
Standard Deviation	.34	.61	.78	1.36	.51	.62

** $P < 0,01$

Based on the results of the Pearson Correlation Analysis presented in Table 7, there was a positive weak correlation between learned helplessness and extrinsic job satisfaction and life satisfaction. A moderately positive association was identified between learned helplessness and intrinsic helplessness and a strong positive relationship was observed between the former and extrinsic helplessness. Intrinsic job satisfaction was positively correlated with extrinsic job satisfaction and life satisfaction; it was also determined to be positively associated with intrinsic helplessness but negatively associated with extrinsic helplessness. Extrinsic job satisfaction was positively correlated with life satisfaction and intrinsic helplessness. Finally, intrinsic helplessness was found to be positively associated with life satisfaction and negatively related to extrinsic helplessness.

Table 8. Regression analysis for predicting life satisfaction

Independent variable	B	Std. Error	β	t	p	R	R ²	F	(model) P
Constant	-1.330	.736		-1.807	.072				
Learned helplessness	.405	.217	.103	1.863	.063	.507	.248	28.417	.000**
Intrinsic job satisfaction	.669	.163	.303	4.085	.000**				
Extrinsic job satisfaction	.288	.122	.165	2.358	.019*				
Intrinsic helplessness	.225	.155	.085	1.447	.149				

** $P < 0,01$

Examination of the results of regression analysis in Table 8 shows that the regression model was statistically significant and that the teachers' intrinsic and extrinsic job satisfaction scores predicted life satisfaction at a level of 24.8% ($R = .507$, $R^2 = .248$, $p < .05$). The participants' learned helplessness and intrinsic helplessness scores were found not to reach the level of predicting life satisfaction.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

In line with the primary objective of this study, the relationships between learned helplessness, job satisfaction, and life satisfaction of physical education teachers were analyzed. As a secondary objective, the participants' life satisfaction and job satisfaction scores were compared in terms of gender, age, whether or not they chose their profession of their own volition, and their hopefulness that the pandemic would reach an end.

Based on the results of descriptive statistics of previous studies, the learned helplessness levels of physical education teachers during the pandemic were determined to be moderate. As per the research findings of Yavaş (2012), teachers' learned helplessness levels were lower than the results we obtained; in other words, during the pandemic, teachers may be said to experience more intense learned helplessness. Accordingly, the negative effects of the pandemic and the hopelessness felt by the majority of the participants concerning whether the pandemic will end and life will return to normal may have exacerbated feelings of helplessness. Turning to job satisfaction, contrary to the expectation that physical education teachers report low levels of job satisfaction during the pandemic, the actual levels were determined to be in the medium to high range. When the results of studies conducted by Dalkılıç (2014) and Akkaya (2015) were examined, the intrinsic-extrinsic job satisfaction levels of the sample group were revealed to be lower than those obtained in the present study measured during the pandemic. This may be explained by the fact that the teachers who were away from school life and forced to teach at home during the pandemic missed their jobs, leading to a greater appreciation of the value of their working lives. Finally, the life satisfaction levels of the participants in the current study were found to be moderate, even in

the midst of the pandemic. The results of research conducted by Acar Arasan (2010), Günaçtı Atasoy (2014), and Ünal (2015) also support this finding. However, in Karababa's study (2012), the participants' life satisfaction levels were determined to be high. There are similarities between life satisfaction levels observed before the pandemic and the results revealed within the scope of the present study.

Concerning the secondary objectives of this study, intrinsic and extrinsic helplessness scores, both subscales of learned helplessness, were found not to differ with respect to gender. As for overall levels of learned helplessness, the male teachers scored higher than their female counterparts, a finding supported by the results of studies by Valas (2001), Düzgün and Hayalioğlu (2006), Cananoğlu (2011), and Taş and Deniz (2018). However, other studies have shown that learned helplessness does not differ significantly by gender (19-45-47-52). Duzgun and Hayalioglu (2006) explained that men may experience more intense learned helplessness than women as a result of the patriarchal nature of Turkish society, such that the roles assigned to men by society shoulder them with greater responsibilities. Considering the converse of this result, that women experience less learned helplessness, one possible explanation is that women are more resistant to giving up (Yavaş, 2012) and hence possess greater psychological strength due to their social roles. Although in Turkish society power is accorded to men, the fact that women are physically able to give birth attests to their obvious capacity for resilience, strength, and determination as well as sensitivity. Regarding intrinsic and extrinsic job satisfaction levels, the other variables we investigated in comparing genders in the present study, no significant differences were observed in terms of gender. The results of studies by Kale (2007), Demirsoy (2009), Mumcu (2014), and Gafa and Dikmenli (2019) were consistent with this finding. In contrast, Alsancak (2010) concluded that men's job satisfaction levels were higher, while Güler (2018) reported that women had higher job satisfaction levels. Nonetheless, the results of the majority of studies in the literature have aligned with our findings. Accordingly, the gender of teachers can be considered to have no significant effect on job satisfaction, as women are now equally involved in the workplace, on a par with men, and can fulfill their responsibilities and establish a strong presence for themselves in their working lives. The teaching profession assigns the same workload to employees, regardless of gender. Considering that gender is not a discriminating factor in job-related situations such as hiring, promotion, administration, wages, and so on, women and men may be expected to experience similar levels of job satisfaction. When the life satisfaction of the participants was examined, the result was similar to that of job satisfaction, the conclusion being that gender did not affect the teachers' life satisfaction. The studies of Şahin (2008), Sarıdemir (2015), Öztürk (2020), and Moran and Çoruk (2021) also produced

results in line with this finding. In studies conducted by Ünal (2015), Kaçay (2015), and Ergün (2016), women's life satisfaction levels were found to be higher than those of men. As with job satisfaction, a review of the literature on life satisfaction revealed that gender was no longer a determining factor since no significant differences were observed with respect to gender in a majority of the studies. This finding can be explained by the fact that in Turkey teaching is a highly respected profession and teachers are valued by society. There is no discrimination between men and women in this profession, and in fact that women may be considered more suitable for teaching. The idea that women's job and life satisfaction scores differ from those of men due to the social roles imposed on them by society, such as that of housewife and mother, has been refuted by the results of recent studies.

As regards the intrinsic and extrinsic helplessness subscales of learned helplessness, no significant differences in terms of age were observed. However, significant differences in learned helplessness overall scores were found between the under 35 and over 45 age groups, as well as between those aged 35-44 and those over 45. The learned helplessness levels of teachers under the age of 35 and between the ages of 35-44 were both lower than those of teachers over the age of 45. Based on these results, we may conclude that helplessness appears to increase with age. Although the results of a study by Çavuşoğlu (2007) were consistent with our findings, Tayfur (2011), in contrast, found that as the age of the sample group increased, the level of learned helplessness decreased. In studies conducted by Kümbül (2002), Tuna (2018), and Kaplan (2019), no significant differences in learned helplessness scores were observed based on age. In the present study, there were no significant differences in extrinsic job satisfaction with respect to age, but a significant difference was found in intrinsic job satisfaction. Teachers under the age of 35 reported lower levels of intrinsic job satisfaction than those over the age of 45, indicating an increase in job satisfaction with age. Kılınç (2012), Akkaya (2015), and Yıldız (2019) also determined that job satisfaction levels of study participants increased with age, whereas Tomrukçu (2010) found job satisfaction decreased with age. The inconsistent results may be due to the fact that the latter study involved participants working in a private institution. Ünal (2015) found that teachers aged 21-30 as well as those in the 41-50 age range both experienced higher levels of job satisfaction levels than those aged between 31-40 years. In studies conducted by Kale (2007), Demirsoy (2009), and Aksoy (2019), no significant differences in job satisfaction in terms of age were observed. In light of these results, the accumulation of professional experience appears to enable people to mature and develop such qualities as accepting the varied circumstances related to working life, assimilating one's job, not reflecting the special problems of being more experienced at one's job, controlling one's emotions, increasing their

ability to adapt to the organization, being objective, earning trust and respect. In other words, the personal and organizational behaviors they acquire with increasing age also add to their job satisfaction. Concerning life satisfaction, a significant difference was observed in terms of age, with participants over the age of 45 scoring higher on life satisfaction than those under the age of 35. As with the job satisfaction levels obtained in the present study, life satisfaction scores also increased with age. Studies by Deveci (2014), Dinç (2019), Dağ (2019), and Akkaya (2020) reported findings consistent with those of the current study. According to the results of Sarıdemir's (2015) study, however, life satisfaction levels trended in the opposite direction, with younger participants experiencing greater life satisfaction than their older peers, whereas Kubilay Özel (2015) found the life satisfaction scores of the participants with an average age of 31-35 to be higher than the other participants, both younger and older. In studies by Acar Arasan (2010), Kıvılcım (2014), Dalkıran (2015), and Yıldız (2019), no significant differences in life satisfaction were found with respect to age. A review of the literature revealed three main findings related to life satisfaction based on the variable of age. First, life satisfaction levels were found to be high among the young, with their youthful energy, then decrease with the approach of middle age. Secondly, life satisfaction subsequently increases after the age of 50, forming a U-shape. Lastly, by gaining life experience as they age, individuals learn to derive more satisfaction from life as they get older, thus increasing their life satisfaction [2-13-17-20-32-39]. The results of the present study support the aforementioned third finding. As with job satisfaction, factors such as individuals' experiences, dignity, the trust in which they are held by society, and reputation all contribute to the increase in life satisfaction that occurs with age. In addition, the fact that young individuals have greater expectations in all areas of life may also explain their relatively low levels of life satisfaction.

No statistically significant differences were found for the learned helplessness and intrinsic and extrinsic helplessness subscale scores according to whether the participant chose their profession of their own volition. As expected, those who chose their profession willingly scored high on job satisfaction, both intrinsic and extrinsic. This result aligns with the findings of Kale (2007), Alsancak (2010), and Karakuzu (2013) also overlap with this result, whereas Akkaya (2015), on the other hand, obtained findings contradicting this result. The present study also determined that physical education teachers who chose their profession willingly had high life satisfaction scores, a finding supported by studies conducted by Şahin (2008), Acar Arasan (2010), and Üçüncü (2019). Accordingly, teachers who choose their profession willingly express positive feelings towards their profession, do not harbor feelings of regret, and love their work; the positive aspects of their working lives also affect their

personal lives. Considering people's ideals and their instinctive need for success, together with the fact that work is financially indispensable given the reality of today's global economy, it is inevitable that working life will affect all other dimensions of life.

In this study, physical education teachers were also asked whether they were hopeful that the pandemic would come to an end. While there were no significant differences in the levels of learned helplessness, extrinsic helplessness, or life satisfaction with regard to this variable, a significant difference in job satisfaction scores was observed in favor of teachers who expressed hope concerning the pandemic. The intrinsic and extrinsic job satisfaction levels of the participants who were hopeful that the pandemic would end and that life would return to normal, who had a positive outlook, were found to be significantly higher than those of their less hopeful peers. Apart from these expected suppositions, the intrinsic learned helplessness scores of the hopeful teachers were significantly higher than those of the hopeless ones, a result that runs counter to the positive perspective of hopeful teachers. Since hopeful teachers would be expected to exhibit low levels of learned helplessness, this finding is surprising. In this case, we surmise that even hopeful teachers may harbor secret anxieties and concerns regarding life and work during the pandemic.

Turning to the relationship between learned helplessness, job satisfaction, and life satisfaction the main issue explored in this study, both life satisfaction and extrinsic job satisfaction were determined to be positively and significantly correlated with intrinsic helplessness and learned helplessness scores. Similarly, intrinsic job satisfaction was found to be positively associated with intrinsic helplessness. These results were unexpected and surprising. In addition, a negative relationship emerged between intrinsic and extrinsic helplessness, such that when the level of either intrinsic or extrinsic helplessness increases, the level of the other decreases. This is thought to result from the fact that the intrinsic and extrinsic scales of learned helplessness measure individuals' attributes in different categories. In other words, the intrinsic helplessness scale measures the interpretation of negative situations by individuals based on intrinsic, self-induced reasons, while extrinsic helplessness measures the interpretation of negative situations due to reasons extrinsic to and independent from the individual, along with environmental factors. The fact that individuals attribute these situations to different reasons, both intrinsic and extrinsic, can be explained by the negative correlation between the scales.

Finally, regression analysis was performed in order to determine to what extent job satisfaction and learned helplessness predicted life satisfaction. Results of multiple linear regression analysis showed that the participating physical education teachers' intrinsic and extrinsic job satisfaction scores predicted life satisfaction by 24.8%. The learned helplessness

variable did not reach the level of predicting life satisfaction. Accordingly, life satisfaction is positively affected by job satisfaction as a dependent variable; although a low-level effect, job satisfaction did predict the life satisfaction levels of the participants during the pandemic. Furthermore, the most important predictors of life satisfaction were determined to be intrinsic and extrinsic job satisfaction. A survey of the literature revealed that positive perfectionism and job satisfaction were found to explain 50% and 57% of life satisfaction, respectively [28]. In another study, perceived organizational support predicted job satisfaction by 48% while organizational trust predicted job satisfaction by 36% [40]. A study by Acar Arasan (2010) concluded that job and life satisfaction scores explained burnout by 27%. According to the results of a study investigating the relationship between attitudes towards leisure time and life satisfaction, the former was found to explain 2% of the total variance in life satisfaction.

In conclusion, based on our findings, the male physical education teachers experienced higher levels of learned helplessness than their female counterparts, while participants over the age of 45 reported higher levels of learned helplessness, intrinsic job satisfaction, and life satisfaction than the younger age groups. The intrinsic-extrinsic job satisfaction and life satisfaction scores of the teachers who chose the profession of their own volition were determined to be higher than those who chose their profession unwillingly, while the intrinsic-extrinsic job satisfaction and intrinsic helplessness scores of the participants hopeful that the pandemic would reach an end were higher than those of their hopeless peers. Statistically significant relationships were observed between learned helplessness, job satisfaction, and life satisfaction.

RECOMMENDATIONS

At the national level, learned helplessness has been studied in children, students, teachers, and employees of other institutions, but not in athletes. A similar study incorporating the Turkish adaptation of the learned helplessness scale could be carried out for athletes. Overtraining on the part of athletes may be related to learned helplessness; such situations would be ripe for examination. On the other hand, while the subject of job and life satisfaction occupies a prominent place in organizational psychology literature, learned helplessness has only recently become a topic of discussion. The phenomenon of learned helplessness can be compared with a number of various psychological conditions, including the perception of leadership in working life, burnout, psychological abuse, and self-concern. We suggest that the learned helplessness levels of teachers, sports administrators, and coaches be studied more comprehensively, on a national level, and that “learned resourcefulness” projects be designed to ameliorate this negative condition.

Conflict of Interest: There is no conflict of interest between the authors.

Statement of Contribution of Researchers:

1.Author: %50

2.Author: %50

Information about the Ethics Committee Permission:Responsibility for any violations that may arise in the work done belongs to the author. Ethics committee approval of the article was obtained with the decision of Istanbul Gelisim University Ethics Committee dated 14.12.2022 and numbered 2022-18.

REFERENCES

- Acar Arasan, B. N. (2010). *Akademisyenlerde yaşam doyumu iş doyumu ve mesleki tükenmişlik düzeylerinin belirlenmesine yönelik bir araştırma* [An study on the determination of life satisfaction, job satisfaction and professional burnout levels in academics] (Unpublished master's thesis). Uşak Üniversitesi Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü, Uşak.
- Akkaya, R. (2015). *Öğretmenlerin kontrol odağı ile iş doyumu arasındaki ilişki* [The relationship between teachers' locus of control and job satisfaction] (Unpublished master's thesis). Adnan Menderes Üniversitesi Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü, Aydın.
- Aksoy, M. (2019). *Beden eğitimi öğretmenlerinin iş doyumu ve tükenmişlik düzeylerinin çeşitli değişkenlere göre incelenmesi* [Examination of physical education teachers' job satisfaction and burnout levels with respect to certain variables](Unpublished master's thesis). Karamanoğlu Mehmetbey Üniversitesi Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü, Karaman.
- Alıç, D. (1995). Örgütler [Organizations]. *Kuram ve Uygulamada Eğitim*, 1(1), 1-40. <https://dergipark.org.tr/tr/pub/kuuey/issue/10394/127183>.
- Alsancak, R. (2010). *İzmir İl sınırlarındaki özel ve kamu'da çalışan beden eğitimi öğretmenlerin iş doyumu düzeylerinin bazı değişkenlere göre belirlenmesi* [Determination of job satisfaction levels of physical education teachers working in private and public sectors in İzmir province with respect to certain variables] (Unpublished master's thesis). Marmara Üniversitesi Sağlık Bilimleri Enstitüsü, İstanbul.
- Aslan, R. (2020). Tarihten günümüze epidemiler, pandemiler ve covid-19 [Epidemics, pandemics and covid-19 from historical times to the present]. *Göller Bölgesi Aylık Ekonomi ve Kültür Dergisi*, 8(85), 32-41. Retrieved from <https://dergipark.org.tr/en/pub/seder/issue/56756/815353>.
- Aydın, G. (1985). *Sosyal başarı eğitimi ve sosyal beceri eğitiminin çocuklarda öğrenilmiş çaresizlik davranışlarının ortadan kaldırılmasına etkisi* [The effect of social achievement training and social skills training on the elimination of learned helplessness behaviors in children] (Unpublished doctoral dissertation). Hacettepe Üniversitesi, Ankara.
- Baycan, A. (1985), *An analysis of several aspects of job satisfaction between different occupational groups* (Unpublished master's thesis). Boğaziçi Üniversitesi Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü, İstanbul.
- Büyüköztürk, Ş., Kılıç Çakmak, E., Akgün, Ö. E., Karadeniz, Ş., and Demirel, F. (2018). *Eğitimde bilimsel araştırma yöntemleri* [Scientific research methods in education] (25). Ankara: Pegem Akademi Yayınları.
- Cananoğlu, E. (2011). *İlköğretim 5. sınıf öğrencilerinin öğrenilmiş çaresizlik düzeyleri ve algıladıkları sınıf atmosferinin sosyodemografik değişkenlere göre incelenmesi* [Examination of primary school 5th grade students' learned helplessness levels and perceived classroom

- atmosphere with respect to sociodemographic variables] (Unpublished master's thesis). Çukurova Üniversitesi Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü, Adana.
- Çavuşoğlu, S. (2007). *Öğrenilmiş çaresizlik teorisi üzerine bir araştırma: Türk kamu yönetiminde reform çabalarının çalışanlar üzerinde davranışsal etkilerinin incelenmesi* [A study on the theory of learned helplessness: Examining the behavioral effects of reform efforts in Turkish public administration on employees] (Unpublished master's thesis). Kocaeli Üniversitesi Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü, Kocaeli.
- Çetinkanat, C. (2000). *Örgütlerde güdülenme ve iş doyumunu* [Motivation and job satisfaction in organizations]. Ankara: Anı Yayıncılık.
- Dağ, A. (2019). *Spor merkezi çalışanlarının özel iyi oluş düzeylerinin iş ve yaşam doyumunu üzerine etkisi: Sakarya ili örneği* [The effect of personal well-being levels on job and life satisfaction of sports center employees: The example of Sakarya province] (Unpublished master's thesis). Sakarya Uygulamalı Bilimler Üniversitesi Lisansüstü Eğitim Enstitüsü, Sakarya.
- Dağlı, A., and Baysal, N. (2016). Yaşam doyumunu ölçeğinin Türkçe 'ye uyarlanması: Geçerlik ve güvenilirlik çalışması [Adaptation of the life satisfaction scale into Turkish: Validity and reliability study]. *Elektronik Sosyal Bilimler Dergisi*, 15 (59) , 0-0. DOI: 10.17755/esosder.263229.
- Dalkılıç, M. (2014). *Farklı bölgelerde çalışan beden eğitimi ve spor öğretim elemanlarının iş doyumunu* [Job satisfaction of physical education and sports instructors working in different regions](Unpublished master's thesis). Gazi Üniversitesi Sağlık Bilimleri Enstitüsü, Ankara.
- Davis, R. V., Weiss, D. J., England, G. W. ve Lofquist, L. H. (1967). *Manuel For The Minnesota Satisfaction Questionnaire Minnesota Studies in Vocational Rehabilitation, XXII. Minneapolis: University of Minnesota. Industrial Relations Center, Word Adjustmen Project.*
- Demirsoy, E. (2009). *Beden eğitimi öğretmenlerinin iş doyumunu ve örgütsel bağlılıkları arasındaki ilişkinin incelenmesi* [Examining the relationship between job satisfaction and organizational commitment in physical education teachers] (Unpublished master's thesis). Abant İzzet Baysal Üniversitesi Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü, Bolu.
- Deveci, S. (2014). *Sağlık çalışanlarının iş doyumunu ve yaşam doyumunu ilişkisi (Antalya Atatürk Devlet Hastanesi hemşireler örneği)* [The relationship between job satisfaction and life satisfaction in healthcare workers (the example of Antalya Atatürk State Hospital nurses)] (Master's thesis). Beykent Üniversitesi Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü, İstanbul.
- Diener, E., Emmons, R. A., Larsen, R. J., and Griffin, S. (1985). The satisfaction with life scale. *Journal of Personality Assessment*, 49 (1), 71-75.
- Dilci, T., and Mermer, B. (2013). 5. Sınıf matematik öğretiminde öğrenilmiş çaresizlik ile soyut düşünme becerisinin bazı değişkenler açısından incelenmesi [An examination of learned helplessness and abstract thinking skills in 5th grade mathematics teaching with respect to certain variables]. *Cumhuriyet Üniversitesi Edebiyat Fakültesi Sosyal Bilimler Dergisi*, 37 (1), 87-106. Retrieved from <https://dergipark.org.tr/en/pub/cumusosbil/issue/4348/59472>
- Dinç, M. (2019). *Sağlık çalışanlarında depresyon riski ile yaşam doyumunun ilişkisi* [The relationship between depression risk and life satisfaction in healthcare workers] (Specialization thesis). Aydın Adnan Menderes Üniversitesi Tıp Fakültesi, Aydın.
- Düzgün, Ş., and Hayalioğlu, H. (2006). Öğrencilerde öğrenilmiş çaresizlik düzeyinin bazı değişkenler açısından incelenmesi [Examining the level of learned helplessness in students with respect to certain variables]. *Kazım Karabekir Eğitim Fakültesi Dergisi*, 1 (13), 404-4013.
- Ergün, B. (2016). *İş doyumunu ve yaşam doyumunu arasındaki ilişki: Öğretmenler üzerine bir araştırma* [The relationship between job satisfaction and life satisfaction: A study on teachers](Unpublished master's thesis). Gazi Üniversitesi Eğitim Bilimleri Enstitüsü, Ankara.
- Gafa, İ., and Dikmenli, Y. (2019). Sınıf öğretmenlerinin iş doyumunu ve iş yaşamındaki yalnızlık düzeylerinin incelenmesi [Examining classroom teachers' job satisfaction and loneliness levels in working life]. *Ahi Evran Üniversitesi Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü Dergisi*, 5(1), 131-150. DOI: 10.31592/aeusbed.567562.
- Güler, M. (2018). *Beden eğitimi öğretmenlerinin zaman yönetimi becerileri ile iş doyumunu arasındaki ilişkinin incelenmesi (Kocaeli ili örneği)* [Examining the relationship between physical education teachers' time management skills and job satisfaction (the example of Kocaeli province)] (Unpublished master's thesis). Kocaeli Üniversitesi Sağlık Bilimleri Enstitüsü, Kocaeli.

Bagkesen, S., and Cepikkurt, F.. (2025). Physical Education Teachers' Learned Helplessness, Job and Life Satisfaction Levels During the Covid-19 Pandemic. *International Journal of Holistic Health, Sports and Recreation*, 4(1), 37-56.

- Günaçtı Atasoy, D. (2014). *Beden eğitimi öğretmenlerinin yaşam doyumunu düzeyleri ve serbest zamana yönelik tutumları [Life satisfaction levels of physical education teachers and their attitudes towards leisure time]* (Unpublished master's thesis). Karadeniz Teknik Üniversitesi Eğitim Bilimleri Enstitüsü, Trabzon.
- Kaçay, Z. (2015). *Beden eğitimi öğretmenlerine göre okul yöneticilerinin etik liderlik davranışlarının örgütsel bağlılık ve yaşam doyumuna etkisi [The effect of ethical leadership behaviors of school administrators on organizational commitment and life satisfaction with regard to physical education teachers]* (Master's thesis). Sakarya Üniversitesi Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü, Sakarya.
- Kale, F. (2007). *Beden eğitimi öğretmenlerinin iş doyum ve tükenmişlik düzeylerinin çeşitli değişkenler açısından incelenmesi [Examination of physical education teachers' job satisfaction and burnout levels with respect to certain variables]* (Unpublished master's thesis). Niğde Üniversitesi Sosyal Bilimler Fakültesi, Niğde.
- Karababa, A. (2012). *Psikolojik danışmanlarda olumlu mükemmeliyetçilik ve olumsuz mükemmeliyetçilik düzeylerinin iş doyum ve yaşam doyumunu yordamadaki rolü [The role of positive perfectionism and negative perfectionism levels in predicting job satisfaction and life satisfaction in psychological counselors]* (Unpublished master's thesis). Pamukkale Üniversitesi Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü, Denizli.
- Kaplan, C. (2019). *Örgütsel adalet algısının öğrenilmiş çaresizlik üzerine etkisi: Mersin Büyükşehir Belediyesi Örneği [The effect of organizational justice perception on learned helplessness: The example of Mersin Metropolitan Municipality]* (Unpublished master's thesis). Mersin Üniversitesi Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü, Mersin.
- Karakuzu, S. (2013). *Denizli il merkezinde bulunan ilkokullarda görev yapan sınıf öğretmenleri ve ortaokullarda görev yapan branş öğretmenlerinin iş doyumunun incelenmesi [Examining job satisfaction in classroom teachers working in primary schools and subject specialist teachers working in secondary schools in the metropolis of Denizli]* (Unpublished master's thesis). Gazi Üniversitesi Eğitim Bilimleri Enstitüsü, Ankara.
- Kılınç, P. (2012). *Gençlik Hizmetleri ve Spor İl Müdürlüğünde çalışan antrenörlerin iş doyumunun belirlenmesi (İç Anadolu bölgesi örneği) [Determination of job satisfaction of trainers working in the Youth Services and Sports Provincial Directorate (the example of the Central Anatolia region)]* (Unpublished master's thesis). Karamanoğlu Mehmetbey Üniversitesi Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü, Karaman.
- Kubilay Özel, N. (2015). *İş doyum ve yaşam doyum arasındaki ilişkinin demografik değişkenler açısından incelenmesi: Konaklama işletmelerinde bir çalışma [Examining the relationship between job satisfaction and life satisfaction in terms of demographic variables: A study on accommodation establishments]* (Unpublished master's thesis). Türk Hava Kurumları Üniversitesi Sosyal Bilimleri Enstitüsü, Ankara.
- Kümbül, B. (2002). *Çalışma hayatında öğrenilmiş çaresizlik olgusu [The phenomenon of learned helplessness in working life]* (Master's thesis). Dokuz Eylül Üniversitesi Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü, İzmir.
- Moran, C., and Çoruk, A. (2021). İlköğretim kurumlarındaki öğretmenlerin duygusal emek davranışları ile yaşam doyum düzeyleri arasındaki ilişki [The relationship between emotional labor behaviors and life satisfaction levels of teachers in primary education institutions]. *Trakya Eğitim Dergisi*, 11 (1), 267-284. DOI:10.24315/tred.705878
- Mumcu, L. (2014). *Beden eğitimi öğretmenlerinin iş doyum ve tükenmişlik düzeylerinin çeşitli değişkenlere göre incelenmesi [Examination of physical education teachers' job satisfaction and burnout levels with respect to certain variables]* (Master's thesis). Karadeniz Teknik Üniversitesi Eğitim Bilimleri Enstitüsü, Trabzon.
- Özguven, İ. E. (2003). *Endüstri psikolojisi*. Ankara: Nobel Yayın Dağıtım.
- Öztürk, B. (2020). *Ortaokullarda görev yapan öğretmenlerin yaşam doyumları ile örgütsel mutlulukları arasındaki ilişki [The relationship between life satisfaction and organizational happiness in secondary school teachers]* (Non-thesis master's project). Pamukkale Üniversitesi Eğitim Bilimleri Enstitüsü, Denizli.
- Parıldar, H. (2020). Tarihte bulaşıcı hastalık salgınları. *Tepecik Eğitim ve Araştırma Hastanesi Dergisi*, 30(Ek sayı), 19-26. doi:10.5222/terh.2020.93764

- Bagkesen, S., and Cepikkurt, F.. (2025). Physical Education Teachers' Learned Helplessness, Job and Life Satisfaction Levels During the Covid-19 Pandemic. *International Journal of Holistic Health, Sports and Recreation*, 4(1), 37-56.
- Quinless, F. W., and Nelson, M. M. (1988). Development of a measure of learned helplessness. *Nursing Research*, 37(1), 11–15. <https://doi.org/10.1097/00006199198801000-00003>.
- Sarıdemir, T. (2015). *Öğretmenlerin algularına göre okul müdürlerinin liderlik stillerinin ve bazı kişisel değişkenlerin öğretmenlerin yaşam doyumu üzerindeki etkisi [The effect of school principals' leadership styles and certain personal variables on teachers' life satisfaction according to teacher perceptions]* (Master's thesis). İstanbul Aydın Üniversitesi Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü, İstanbul.
- Sarıkaya, Ş. (2019). *Öğretmenlerin iş doyumunun yordayıcısı olarak örgütsel güven ve örgütsel destek algısı [Perception of organizational trust and organizational support as a predictor of teachers' job satisfaction]* (Unpublished master's thesis). Marmara Üniversitesi- İstanbul Sabahattin Zaim Üniversitesi Ortak Yüksek Lisans Programı, İstanbul.
- Şahin, Ş. (2008). *Beden eğitimi öğretmenlerinin tükenmişlik ve yaşam doyumu düzeyleri [Burnout and life satisfaction levels of physical education teachers]* (Unpublished master's thesis). Mersin Üniversitesi Sağlık Bilimleri Enstitüsü, Mersin.
- Taş, S.,and Deniz, S. (2018). Sekizinci sınıf öğrencilerinin matematiğe yönelik öğrenilmiş çaresizliklerinin yordanması: problem çözme becerisi ve bilişsel esneklik [Predicting 8th grade students' learned helplessness towards mathematics: problem solving skills and cognitive flexibility]. *Türk Bilgisayar ve Matematik Eğitim Dergisi*, 9 (3), 618-635. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.17762/turcomat.v9i3>. 189.
- Tayfur, Ö. (2011). *Çalışma hayatında öğrenilmiş çaresizlik ve tükenmişliğin nedenleri ve sonuçları üzerine bir çalışma [A study on the causes and consequences of learned helplessness and burnout in working life]*(Unpublished doctoral dissertation). Hacettepe Üniversitesi Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü, Ankara.
- Tomrukçu, Ç. (2010). *Özel ve kamuya ait ilköğretim kurumlarında çalışan öğretmenlerin yaşam ve iş doyumu düzeyleri [Life and job satisfaction levels of teachers working in private and public primary education institutions]* (Unpublished master's thesis). Ondokuz Mayıs Üniversitesi Eğitim Bilimleri Enstitüsü, Samsun.
- Tuna, N. (2018). *Bireylerde Kariyer Algısı ve örgütlerde yetenek yönetimi uygulamalarının çalışanların öğrenilmiş çaresizlik üzerindeki rolü [The role of career perception in individuals and talent management practices in organizations on learned helplessness in employees]* (Unpublished master's thesis). İstanbul Üniversitesi Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü, İstanbul.
- Tura, M.(2012). *İlköğretim Okulu Müdürlerinin Liderlik Stillerinin Öğretmenlerin İş doyumuna Etkisi/Karacabey İlçesi Örneği [The Effect of Primary School Principals' Leadership Styles on Teachers' Job Satisfaction/The Example of Karacabey District]* (Unpublished master's thesis). Balıkesir Üniversitesi Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü, Balıkesir.
- Ural, C. P. (2009). *Psikoşiddete maruz kalmış öğretmenlerin öğrenilmiş çaresizlik düzeylerinin incelenmesi [Examination of learned helplessness levels in teachers exposed to psychological violence]* (Unpublished master's thesis). Sakarya Üniversitesi Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü, Sakarya.
- Üçüncü, T. (2019). *İstanbul Beylikdüzü İlçesine bağlı ilk ve ortaokullarda görev yapmakta olan öğretmenlerde iş ve yaşam doyumunun değerlendirilmesi [Evaluation of job and life satisfaction of teachers working in primary and secondary schools in Beylikdüzü, Istanbul]*. (Public health dissertation). İstanbul Üniversitesi Cerrahpaşa Tıp Fakültesi, İstanbul.
- Ünal, A. (2015). *İş doyumunu, yaşam doyumunu ve yaşam anlamları değişkenlerinin ilköğretim ve ortaokul öğretmenlerinin mesleki bağlılıkları üzerine etkisi [The effects of job satisfaction, life satisfaction and meaning of life variables on primary and secondary school teachers' professional commitment]*(Unpublished master's thesis). Ondokuz Mayıs Üniversitesi Eğitim Bilimleri Enstitüsü, Samsun.
- Valas, H. (2001). Learned helplessness and psychological adjustment I: Effects of age, gender, and academic achievement. *Scandinavian Journal of Educational Research*, 45(1), 71-90.
- Yavaş, T. (2012). *Ortaöğretim okul yöneticileri ve öğretmenlerinin öğrenilmiş çaresizlik, tükenmişlik ve öz-yeterlilik algularının örgütsel öğrenme üzerine etkileri [The effects of secondary school administrators' and teachers' perceptions of learned helplessness, burnout and self-efficacy on organizational learning]* (Unpublished doctoral dissertation). Fırat Üniversitesi Eğitim Bilimleri Enstitüsü, Elazığ.

Bagkesen, S., and Cepikkurt, F.. (2025). Physical Education Teachers' Learned Helplessness, Job and Life Satisfaction Levels During the Covid-19 Pandemic. *International Journal of Holistic Health, Sports and Recreation*, 4(1), 37-56.

Yenilmez, Ö. (2020). İşletme bölümü öğrencilerinin matematikte öğrenilmiş çaresizlik düzeylerinin incelenmesi [Examination of learned helplessness levels of business students in mathematics].*Eskişehir Osmangazi Üniversitesi Türk Dünyası Uygulama ve Araştırma Merkezi Eğitim Dergisi*, 5(1), 13-24. Retrieved from <https://dergipark.org.tr/en/pub/estudamegitim/issue/53306/695895>.

Yıldız, E. (2019). *Okul öncesi öğretmenlerinin örgütsel sosyalleşme ve yaşam doyumu düzeylerinin incelenmesi (Siverek ilçesi örneği)* [Examination of the organizational socialization and life satisfaction levels of preschool teachers (the example of Siverek district)] (Unpublished master's thesis). Gazi Üniversitesi Eğitim Bilimleri Enstitüsü, Ankara.

This paper is licensed under a **Creative Commons Atıf 4.0 International (CC BY 4.0)**